

Horizon 2020 Societal challenge 5: Climate action, environment, resource efficiency and raw materials

TiPACCs

Tipping Points in Antarctic Climate Components

GA no 820575

Research and Innovation Action (RIA)

Start date: 1st August 2019. End date: 30th July 2023

Deliverable number:	D 17
Deliverable name:	Project website
WP / WP number:	WP4
Delivery due date:	Project month 3 (31/10/2019)
Actual date of submission:	30/10/2019
Dissemination level:	Public
Lead beneficiary:	NORCE
Responsible scientist/administrator:	Jørund Raukleiv Strømsøe
Contributor(s):	Jørund Raukleiv Strømsøe (NORCE)
Internal reviewer:	Petra Langebroek (NORCE)

1. Changes with respect to the DoA

No changes.

2. Dissemination and uptake

This deliverable public.

3. Short Summary of results (< 250 words)

Deliverable 4.1 Project website is associated with work package 4, Communication, Dissemination, Exploitation and Decision support, more specifically task 4.1 Social Media strategy (M1-M48). A project website is a key dissemination and communication tool and usually the first place to look for information. Well-designed project website is therefore very important for a project like TiPACCs. At www.tipaccs.eu information etc. about the TiPACCs project, i.e. the projects overall objectives, news, outreach activities, positions can be found. We have an internal/ access restricted section on the website that serves as a platform for interaction between the participants of the project. This is a way to share documents and files in order to get a good workflow among the participants in the project. The webpage is structured in six sections;

- Home
- About
- News
- Outreach
- Positions
- Contact

The website is “living” and more information/ content will be provided if needs or requests comes up.

4. Evidence of accomplishment

The website internet address is www.tipaccs.eu. Under, three screenshots from the project website can be seen.

Where ocean and ice meet...

Photo: Svein Østerhus

About TiPACCs

One of today's greatest challenges is to understand the impacts of global warming on our environment and societies. One particular important, but highly uncertain, impact is the ongoing sea level rise due to melting ice sheets. TiPACCs assesses the possibility of near-future irreversible changes, so-called **tipping points**, in the Southern Ocean and the Antarctic Ice Sheet. Crossing these tipping points has significant societal consequences.

TiPACCs is a EU Horizon 2020 funded project that will run from August 2019 until July 2023.

[Learn more.](#)

News

Elmer/Ice course for beginners – Reykjavik – 28-29 October 2019

Jørund Strømsoe ● October 14, 2019

The University of Iceland, in collaboration with CSC (Finland) and IGE (France) is organizing a...

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Last week about 20 European researchers gathered in Bergen, and it was time to properly...

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Presenting TiPACCs in Norwegian broadcasting media

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The same day as the start of the TiPACCs Kick-off meeting in Bergen, Norway NORCE...

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TiPACCs members at FRISP 2019

Jørund Strømsoe ● September 19, 2019

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